

WORD CLASSES AND THEIR USES IN ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the results of general research on English grammar phrases, nouns, adjectives and adverbs are presented and they are presented with examples.

The structure of language and how different words fit together are referred to as grammar. Knowing the laws of English grammar should help you produce clear and coherent phrases. All English words can be divided into several categories, known as word classes. A sentence is made up of nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, prepositions, and conjunctions.

The use of a word in context determines its class. Suffixes (additions to words that create new words) are used in some terms to denote the class to which they belong. These suffixes aren't usually sufficient in defining the classification of a word. The suffix -ly, for example, is frequently used in adverbs (slowly, proudly), but it can also be found in adjectives (cowardly, homely, masculine). We can also convert words from one class to another, even if they have suffixes that are unique to their original class: an engineer, to engineer; a negative answer, to negative.

Words not only convey meaning, but they also have an impact. Words are categorized

based on their function in a phrase or sentence. There are nine separate word classes in English. Nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs are the four types of words. These are lexical in nature, providing the basic meaning of a phrase or sentence. The other five word classes are prepositions, pronouns, determiners, conjunctions, and interjections. These are useful in nature because they provide structural and relational info.

A noun is a word that is used to describe someone or something.

A verb is a word that describes what someone does or what happens.

The properties of a noun are described by an adjective.

A term that comprises information about a verb, an adjective, and another adverb is known as an adverb.

A pronoun is a word that is used to substitute a common noun.

A conjunction is a word or phrase that joins the words or sentences.

Word classes exhibit varying degrees of sensitivity and susceptibility to contact-induced linguistic change (borrowing) and language mixing in conversation (code switching). Our contribution focuses on the hierarchical character of word class arrangement as seen in language contact settings. We investigate some of the characteristics that follow the integration of borrowed items in specific word classes and evaluate generalizations that have addressed the subject of borrowing limits on specific categories. Then, we look at some of the findings from the bilingual corpus study, as well as their implications for an explanatory model of borrowing and the role of word classes in contact-induced change.

Although the preceding description may give the idea that any single word inside a single meaning belongs solely to one word class, this is not the case. This flexibility in word class membership is unique to English among European languages, as several would require distinct endings to indicate the class of the term.

A really good teacher thinks hard about likely errors and then he/she plans the lesson carefully.

Word classes:

noun (n.) verb (v.) adjective (adj.) adverb (adv.) pronoun (pron.)
 article (art.) conjunction (conj.) preposition (prep.)

A	really	good	teacher	thinks	hard	about	likely
a) art.	b) adv.	c) adj.	d) n.	e) v.	f) adv.	g) prep.	h) adj.
errors	and	then	he/she	plans	the	lesson	carefully
i) n.	j) conj.	k) adv.	l) pron.	m) n.	n) art.	o) n.	p) adv.

Tense is a grammatical phrase that describes time; that is, whether an action or situation occurred in the past, is currently occurring, or will occur in the future. Tense is not confined to these applications, but they are the most common. Let us look at the three major tenses: past, present, and future, as well as their functions and structures. We'll also look at aspect, which is a vital component of tense, and how to build tenses using inflections. Tense conveys an event's place in time. The accompanying verb forms identify the various tenses. There are three basic tenses: past, present, and future. In English, each of these tenses can have four major aspects: simple, perfect, and continuous (also known as progressive), and perfect continuous. The perfect aspect is generated by the verb to have, but the

continuous aspect is formed by the verb to be. The tenses show that actions occur at a given point in time. Auxiliaries and verbs are used to construct them. There are three primary verb tenses in English grammar: present, past, and future. For example, the Present Simple is employed to show action that takes place on a regular or routine basis. To utilize this tense, the verb's root form (Verb 1) must be used. In Past Simple, the second form of the (Verb 2) is used to show an event that happened at a specific time in the past. The construction of verb tenses is also aided by auxiliaries. In Continuous, for example, the forms of TO BE are commonly used.

Verb tenses are divided into three categories: past, present, and future. The term "past" refers to previously occurring occurrences (e.g., earlier in the day,

yesterday, last week, three years ago). The present tense is used to describe what is happening right now or what is now taking place. The future tense is used to describe events that have yet to occur.

Furthermore, multiple tenses are used to discuss or write about different times. For example, we usually use present tense verb forms to refer to conditions, events, or activities that happened or are happening right now. Past tense verb forms are often used to depict events, states, or activities that occurred in the past. Past tense expressions can also be used to allude to the present situation, for example, to be polite or indirect. Things that occur within the confines of a book should be addressed in the same way that facts and generalizations are. This applies to fictitious storylines in novels, films, plays, and so forth. Use the present simple to describe the major events or acts; other tenses might be used to indicate different timeframes within the narrative. Tense expressions are frequently linked with aspect expressions; what are conventionally considered tenses (in languages such as Latin) may be seen as tense-aspect combos in current analysis. Verbs are frequently conjugated for mood, and because the three categories are not always displayed independently, some languages may be regarded as having a combined tense-aspect-mood (TAM) system.

Interpret the ways in which person is indicated in English grammar

A grammatical person is a person who is participating in an event, such as the person speaking, the person being talked to, or the person being talked about. To achieve grammatical people, pronouns are used, which are words that take the place

of a noun to make communication easier. In the first person, the speaker addresses himself or herself. The second person refers to the individual to whom someone is speaking or writing.

In English grammar, the person category denotes whether a subject is speaking about itself (first person—I or we), being spoken to (second person—you), or being discussed (third person—he, she, it, or they). A grammatical person is occasionally referred to as a "person." When we communicate about ourselves, our ideas, and the things that happen to us, we usually use the first person. The use of first-person pronouns is the most telling sign that a phrase is written in the first person. The pronouns are highlighted in the first sentence of this paragraph. We, us, our, and ourselves are all first-person pronouns. They are plural first-person pronouns. Singular first-person pronouns include I, me, my, mine, and myself.

The first-person point of view is used in many stories and books. You are inside a character's head in this type of narrative, experiencing the story evolve through their eyes. The person (or people) being addressed has the second-person point of view. This is the "you" point of view. The usage of second-person pronouns: you, your, yours, yourself, yourselves, is, once again, the most obvious evidence of the second person. Auxiliary verbs combine with the principal verb in the phrase to generate a distinct, specialized meaning. The three major auxiliary verbs are do, have, and be, all of which can be conjugated to indicate tense and person.

The individual (or people) being discussed has the third-person point of view. He, him, his, himself, she, her, hers, herself, it, its, itself, they, them, their, theirs, and

themselves are examples of third-person pronouns. There are many stories and books written in the third person. A disembodied narrator narrates what the characters do and what happens to them in this style of fiction. You don't see a character's thoughts and feelings as directly as you would in a first-person narrative, but the narrator frequently explains the primary character's thoughts and feelings about what's going on. When people talk about themselves, they usually do it in the first person. It would be strange to talk about yourself in the third person all the time, but you could do it for humorous effect or to catch someone's attention.

The auxiliary verb do is used when we want to ask inquiries or make verbs negative. In the present tense and third person singular, we conjugate do into does. *Interpret the ways in which number is indicated in English grammar*

You may believe that number is exclusively relevant to your math lesson and has nothing to do with English or language. You couldn't be more mistaken. The term "number" is more than just a numerical phrase used in mathematics and accounting. There is also a number in English grammar that you may have studied about in literature class. The word number in English grammar refers to the contrast between single and plural. Number also applies to nouns, pronouns, verbs, and adjectives. The number indicates whether a noun, pronoun, verb, or adjective is singular or plural in a sentence. The count of a noun or pronoun is referred to as the number in grammar.

There are boy-boys, it-they, and so on, for example.

Numbers of various kinds:

Numbers can be separated into two categories.

Singular and Plural forms

It's a noun or pronoun with only one count. Objects include things like a pen, a table, an aunt, a father, a goose, and so on.

Numbers in their plural form:

The count refers to the number of nouns or pronouns that are counted.

Only a few instances include tables, tables, fathers, and others.

The counting noun in a sentence is what a number is all about. In English grammar, number indicates the number of people in a sentence. In comparison to many other languages, English has it relatively easy because many words (especially adjectives) do not change when their grammatical number changes. For instance, we say "smelly dog" and "smelly dogs." The word "smelly" remains the same. Many other languages are not like this.

Small numbers ranging from one to ten (or one to nine, depending on the style guide) should normally be spelt out. Larger numbers (those more than 10) are written in numerals. Nouns change when a word's grammatical number shifts. When nouns become plural, they often add a "s" (e.g., "cat" becomes "cats"), but verbs may lose a "s" (e.g., "he plays" becomes "they play") and some determiners change their forms (e.g., "this" becomes "these"). Ordinal numerals include first, second, and third. We use them to organize stuff. Ordinal numbers are the most often used determiners. Ordinal numbers are widely used as determiners (before nouns) with other determiners like as articles (a/an, the) and possessives (my, your) in front of them:

He'd failed the sixth science exam in a row.

Her twenty-first birthday is being celebrated with friends in Malaysia.

Cardinal numbers include one, five, eleven, and two hundred. As determiners, we most usually utilize cardinal numbers (before nouns). When we employ them in this way, we can put other determiners in front of them, such as articles (a/an, the) and possessives (my, your). We can use cardinal numbers + before determiners (as suggested by one of my friends):

She adores animals and currently owns two dogs, three cats, and one bunny.

We usually say hundred, thousand, and million. When we want to emphasize a

number, we only use the numbers one hundred, one thousand, and one million:

What would you do if you were awarded a million euros?

In a nutshell, these are the different word classes in English. Word classes are frequently problematic for English learners because they are not aware that they are as much a part of grammar as tenses and so change depending on the situation. Understanding word classes and how they change is the first step in understanding English grammar.

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